

Cognitive Science
Mathematics for Cognitive Science
--Manuscript Draft--

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Corresponding Author:	Venkata Rayudu Posina, B.Tech Independent Scientist Hyderabad, Telangana INDIA
Corresponding Author Secondary Information:	
Corresponding Author's Institution:	Independent Scientist
Corresponding Author's Secondary Institution:	
First Author:	Venkata Rayudu Posina, B.Tech
First Author Secondary Information:	
Order of Authors:	Venkata Rayudu Posina, B.Tech
Order of Authors Secondary Information:	
Abstract:	<p>That the state-of-affairs of cognitive science is not good is brought into figural salience in "What happened to cognitive science?" (Núñez et al., 2019). We extend their objective description of 'what's wrong' to a prescription of 'how to correct'. Cognitive science, in its quest to elucidate 'how we know', embraces a long list of subjects, while ignoring Mathematics (Fig. 1a, Núñez et al., 2019). Mathematics is known for making the unknown to be known (cf. solving for unknowns). This acknowledgement naturally raises the question: does mathematical knowing inform knowing in general? Here we show that drawing parallels to mathematical knowing can facilitate the advancement of cognitive science (Lawvere, 1994).</p>

To,

Professor Richard P. Cooper

Executive Editor

Cognitive Science

Dear Professor Cooper,

I am herewith submitting my manuscript “Mathematics for Cognitive Science” to be considered for publication as a ‘Letter To The Editor’ in your journal Cognitive Science. My Letter was motivated by the unsatisfactory contemporary state-of-affairs of cognitive science highlighted in the recent study:

Núñez, R. et al. What happened to cognitive science? *Nat. Hum. Behav.* 3, 782-791 (2019).

Based on the kinship between mathematics [in particular and science in general] and cognition (cf. cognition is science writ small; *Daedalus* 135: 86, 2006), I make a case for mathematical abstraction as a pathway for the advancement of cognitive science. It may be noted here that the parallels between mathematical knowing and knowing in general, which I bring into focus, provide a means “to connect cognitive science theories to computational foundations” (*Nat. Hum. Behav.* 3: 782, 2019).

I outline the mathematics of calculating representation(s)—a fundamental notion in cognitive science. I felt that it is important to explicitly state that the notion of ‘representation’ figuring in the foundational tenet—“cognition is computation of representations” (Nat. Hum. Behav. 3, 782, 2019)—of cognitive science is indispensable in theorizing about cognition. However, we may need to replace computation with calculation [of representations] so as to move past the computer metaphor and bring the insights of functorial semantics to bear on cognitive science. Representation (or model), according to functorial semantics, is an interpretation of a theory into a background category (Reprints in Theory and Applications of Categories 5, 8-11, 2004). The category of all models of a theory T in a background B is a functor category B^T of all functorial interpretations $T \rightarrow B$ of the theory T in the background B . Changing theories ($T1 \rightarrow T2$) induces contravariant changes in representations ($B^{T2} \rightarrow B^{T1}$), while changing backgrounds ($B1 \rightarrow B2$) induces covariant changes in representations ($B1^T \rightarrow B2^T$). I discuss these mathematical insights into representation in a manner readily accessible to the multidisciplinary audience of your journal. This discussion can help insure against: throwing the baby (representation) with bathwater (hexagon; Fig 1a in Nat. Hum. Behav. 3, 782, 2019).

In closing, my manuscript brings out the reach of functorial semantics [of calculating representations] into sharper focus so as to facilitate ready recognition of the relevance of functorial semantics for the development of cognitive science.

If I may, the following may be considered for reviewing my manuscript since they are experts on cognitive science and category theory.

Professor Michael A. Arbib (arbib@usc.edu)

Professor Andrée C. Ehresmann (ehres@u-picardie.fr)

Professor F. William Lawvere (wlawvere@buffalo.edu)

Professor Giuseppe Longo (Giuseppe.Longo@ens.fr)

I earnestly hope that you will find my manuscript suitable for publication in your journal Cognitive Science. I sincerely thank you for your kind consideration of my manuscript and I eagerly look forward to hearing from you.

Thanking you,

Yours truly,

Venkata Rayudu Posina

Affiliation:

Independent Scientist

Google Scholar Profile:

<https://scholar.google.co.in/citations?user=cnMxV9MAAAAJ&hl=en&oi=ao>

ORCID ID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-3040-9224>

Address for Correspondence:

Venkata Rayudu Posina, 101- B2 Swathi Heights, A. S. Rao Nagar, Hyderabad - 500062,

Telangana, India

Email: posinavrayudu@gmail.com, Tel: +91-963-222-4686

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5 **Author:** Venkata Rayudu Posina

6

7 **Affiliation:**

8 Independent Scientist

9 Google Scholar Profile:

10 <https://scholar.google.co.in/citations?user=cnMxV9MAAAAJ&hl=en&oi=ao>

11 ORCID ID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-3040-9224>

12 **Address for Correspondence:**

13 Venkata Rayudu Posina, 101- B2 Swathi Heights, A. S. Rao Nagar, Hyderabad - 500062,

14 Telangana, India

15 Email: posinavrayudu@gmail.com, Tel: +91-963-222-4686

16 That the state-of-affairs of cognitive science is not good is brought into figural salience in “What
17 happened to cognitive science?” (Núñez et al., 2019). We extend their objective description of
18 ‘what’s wrong’ to a prescription of ‘how to correct’. Cognitive science, in its quest to elucidate
19 ‘how we know’, embraces a long list of subjects, while ignoring Mathematics (Fig. 1a, Núñez et
20 al., 2019). Mathematics is known for making the unknown to be known (cf. solving for
21 unknowns). This acknowledgement naturally raises the question: does mathematical knowing
22 inform knowing in general? Here we show that drawing parallels to mathematical knowing can
23 facilitate the advancement of cognitive science (Lawvere, 1994).

24 What is cognition? One scientific approach is to answer: what is cognition good for?
25 Science—reconstructing reality from appearances—is the signature product of human cognition.
26 Since a product retains traces of the process that gave rise to the product, a declarative
27 understanding [but not merely procedural knowledge] of the scientific reconstruction of reality
28 from planned perception constitutes the foundations of the science of cognition. The
29 mathematical basis of scientific reconstruction across disciplines is: comparison of the observed
30 variation with constancy (Lawvere & Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 125-126, 148-152). Reality is
31 inferred from appearances by establishing an isomorphism between perceived (generalized
32 points) and actual (points). The relationship between points and generalized points involved in
33 scientific reconstruction is analogous to the relationship between stimuli and percepts:
34 reconstruction of the causes that gave rise to sensation (Albright, 2015). The process of going
35 from stimuli to percepts involves a two-step process of sensation followed by interpretation
36 (Croner & Albright, 1999), which is reminiscent of the double-dualization involved in going
37 from points to generalized points. Therefore, we can consider generalized points of scientific

38 reconstruction of reality as an abstraction of conscious percepts of ordinary cognition (Lawvere,
39 2004a).

40 With conscious experiences as representations (Chalmers, 2006) in the foundational tenet of
41 “cognition is computation of representations” (Núñez et al., 2019, p. 782), a comprehensive
42 theory of cognition naturally subsumes conscious experiences. Consciousness, the totality of
43 conscious experiences (Koch, 2018), can be construed as a mathematical category of conscious
44 experiences along with their transformations (Lawvere & Schanuel, 2009, p. 21). Beginning
45 with a theory of conscious experiences, say, ‘conscious experience is an interpretation of
46 sensation’ (alluded to earlier) we obtain a category of two-sequential functions as the category of
47 models of conscious experiences (Posina, Ghista & Roy, 2017). The theory ‘conscious
48 experience is an interpretation of sensation’ is also a mathematical category consisting of three
49 component structural objects (stimuli, neural codes, conscious percepts) and two component
50 structural maps (sensation, interpretation; Lawvere & Schanuel, 2009, pp. 149-150). More
51 broadly, for each abstract theory of conscious experiences we obtain a corresponding category of
52 models. With every theory of the category of conscious experiences construed as a graph or a
53 small category (Lawvere, 2016; Lawvere & Schanuel, 2009, p. 149, 199-203), we obtain a
54 category of models, which is a functor category (a category whose objects are functorial
55 interpretations of a theory category into a background category). The category of all functor
56 categories subsumes every possible value of every property of each object of the category of
57 conscious experiences, i.e. constitutes an adequate characterization of consciousness (Lawvere &
58 Schanuel, 2009, pp. 370-371). This category of all functor categories is the space of all possible
59 mathematical answers to the question: What is consciousness? (This is analogous to the scenario
60 where the set $N = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ of natural numbers can be thought of as the set of all answers to

61 the question: What is the size of X , where X is any set?) Furthermore, since representations of a
62 given category of particulars are functorial interpretations of a theory into a background
63 category, representations of particulars vary contravariantly with changes in theory and
64 covariantly with background changes (Lawvere, 1994, p. 46; Lawvere & Rosebrugh, 2003, pp.
65 120-122). In cognitive terminology, conscious experiences (representations) vary as a function
66 of both mental concepts (theories) and intuitions (backgrounds); functorial semantics of
67 mathematical knowing spells out how, i.e., provides a mathematical account of calculating
68 representations of mathematical objects (Posina, Ghista & Roy, 2017; Lawvere, 2004b).

69 Returning to reality, if reality were the category of sets, then three-valued properties guarantee
70 the recovery of “reality” from perception (Lawvere, 2004a). Of course, reality is not a set; it’s
71 much more structured than the structure-less sets. For instance, reality is self-representing since
72 its representations: collective science and individual perception are parts—reflective parts—of
73 the reality (Lawvere & Schanuel, 2009, pp. 84-85). So, reality can be modeled as the self-
74 representing mathematical category of categories, wherein a mathematical category (e.g.
75 reflexive graphs) is represented in its discrete-and-constant subcategory (Lawvere, 2004b, p. 12;
76 see also Lawvere, 2003, p. 215, 217). This correspondence suggests calculation of the basic
77 types-of-knowing (objects analogous to the three-element set in the category of sets) in
78 mathematical categories that are reflective of reality such as the category of categories. In doing
79 so, we can address two related foundational questions:

80 1. What is the nature of reconstructable reality (the structure of reality that can be reconstructed
81 from appearances)?

82 2. What is the nature of revealing appearances (the structure of appearances that is conducive for
83 reconstructing reality)?

84 More fundamentally, reality is often analyzed into the categories of Being and Becoming,
85 which is not satisfactory since reality consists, as noted above, of parts—individual cognition
86 and collective science—reflective of the reality. Hence we need a mathematical category of
87 Reflecting in addition to the categories of Being and Becoming in order to bridge the two
88 categories of objective reality on the one hand and its subjective reflections on the other. A
89 mathematical category of Reflecting can be objectified along the lines of the objectification of
90 Being and Becoming as mathematical categories of reflexive graphs (exemplifying unity) and
91 dynamical systems (change), respectively (Lawvere, 1991, 1992, 2007). The mathematical
92 category of Reflecting makes room for the basis of science—human cognition—in the scientific
93 representation of reality.

94 In closing, it must be noted that the foundational tenet—“cognition is computation of
95 representations” (Núñez et al., 2019, p. 782)—is still viable provided we shift our focus from
96 ‘computation’ to ‘representation’, move on from the computer metaphor along with its attendant
97 conceptual baggage (cf. hardware vs. software), and build on the definitive mathematical
98 understanding of calculating representations (Lawvere, 2004b). Furthermore, however exciting
99 they may be, we also need to shift our focus away from the excitement of winning games such as
100 Go, especially because of the anti-scientific faith that they demand (Editorial, 2016) and start
101 focusing on the development of theory, as the Cognitive Science Society correctly decided:
102 “greater effort must be made to connect cognitive science theories to computational foundations”
103 (Núñez et al., 2019, p. 789). Here ‘computational foundations’ can be understood as
104 ‘foundations of calculating representations’, i.e. functorial semantics (Lawvere, 2004b).

105 Summing it all, we suggest that functorial semantics is to cognition what calculus is to physics,
106 i.e. the mathematics needed for the development of cognitive science (Lawvere, 1994, p. 43, 55;
107 Lawvere, 1999, p. 412).

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Venkata Rayudu Posina <posinavrayudu@gmail.com>

Action Letter 19-274

1 message

Cognitive Science <em@editorialmanager.com>
Reply-To: Cognitive Science <mayahmed@indiana.edu>
To: Venkata Rayudu Posina <posinavrayudu@gmail.com>

Tue, Sep 24, 2019 at 10:28 PM

Dear Mr. Venkata Posina,

I write concerning your letter "Mathematics for Cognitive Science", which was recently submitted to *Cognitive Science*. I regret to inform you that I have decided that we are unable to consider your manuscript for publication in *Cognitive Science*.

The Núñez et al. article has certainly attracted attention, and a set of commentaries is scheduled to appear in our sister journal, *Topics in Cognitive Science*, next month. Given this I don't think that *Cognitive Science* is the right place for your letter. However, I'm also not convinced that your letter would be a good fit for *Topics in Cognitive Science* either. I completely agree that mathematics has an important role to play in the discipline of cognitive science, particularly in formalising theory (which is consistent with your conclusion "that functorial semantics is ... the mathematics needed for the development of cognitive science"). I have even occasionally thought I should write a book with exactly the title of your letter. Yet I am sure that the majority of our readers will not find your arguments compelling. Even though I have some familiarity with category theory myself – more, I believe, than most cognitive scientists – I find your arguments too abstract. If mathematics is to contribute, then it must do more than just formalise, that formalisation must yield some concrete gain or development in theory.

While I appreciate this outcome will be disappointing, I hope that you will appreciate that I have come to this decision quickly. Let me close by thanking you for considering *Cognitive Science*. I hope the unfavorable outcome on this occasion will not prevent you from submitting your best interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary work on cognitive function, processes or theory, to *Cognitive Science* in the future.

Regards,

Rick Cooper
Executive Editor,
Cognitive Science

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